

EXPLORING MATURITY IN INFORMATION SYSTEMS AND IMPACT OF AI

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Abstract: Information systems (IS) support both the strategic objectives and operational processes of organizations. Maturity models have emerged as valuable tools to help organizations assess their current state and guide their progress toward higher maturity levels. This study conducts a systematic literature review to examine whether common structural components can be identified across maturity models in the IS domain. Sixteen maturity models developed for specific applications are analyzed, revealing recurring elements such as design approaches, assessment methods, and common dimensions. In addition, the impact of artificial intelligence on maturity is explored, highlighting its potential to accelerate progression across maturity stages while also introducing new challenges.

Keywords: information system, artificial intelligence, maturity model, literature review

Apstrakt: Informacioni sistemi (IS) podržavaju strateške ciljeve i operativne procese organizacija. Modeli zrelosti su se pojavili kao vredni alati koji pomažu organizacijama da procene svoje trenutno stanje i usmere napredak ka višim nivoima zrelosti. Ovaj rad sprovodi pregled literature kako bi ispitaio da li se zajedničke strukturne komponente mogu identifikovati svim modelima zrelosti u oblasti informacionih sistema. Analizirano je šesnaest modela zrelosti razvijenih za specifične primene, otkrivajući elemente koji se ponavljaju kao što su pristupi dizajnu, metode ocene zrelosti i zajedničke dimenzije. Pored toga, istražuje se uticaj veštačke inteligencije na zrelost, ističući njen potencijal da ubrza napredak kroz faze zrelosti, istovremeno uvodeći nove izazove.

Ključne reči: informacioni sistem, veštačka inteligencija, model zrelosti, pregled literature

1. INTRODUCTION

Information systems (IS) are one of the most relevant components of the modern business environment, shaping how organizations operate, compete, and deliver value. They enable organizations to collect, process, and share data in an integrated and timely manner, thereby creating significant opportunities for improving organizational performance (Al-Mamary et al., 2014). Information systems are typically designed to support activities within each functional area, and their quality directly affects operational efficiency and overall business outcomes (Almazán et al., 2017). As organizations strive to keep pace with an increasingly dynamic business landscape, they seek approaches to assess their current capabilities and identify opportunities for

improvement. Maturity models (MMs) have emerged as widely used instruments positioning an organization along the path to target state of maturity, typically defining a series of maturity levels through which an organization or process advances. The descriptive elements of each level often serve as guidelines for achieving higher stages of maturity. During a maturity assessment, a snapshot of the organization is created based on predefined criteria, providing a basis for improvement initiatives (Becker et al., 2009). The Capability Maturity Model (CMM) has been particularly influential, shaping the design and development of numerous maturity models within IS research. The emergence of artificial intelligence (AI) marks a significant transformation in the IS landscape, automating decision-making, enabling real-time analytics, and driving new forms of value creation. This technological shift also has important implications for maturity model research, as it both challenges the assumptions of existing models and presents opportunities to enhance them. On one hand, AI may disrupt traditional maturity pathways by accelerating progression through maturity stages and introducing entirely new dimensions of maturity that were previously absent. On the other hand, AI can actively support the development and application of maturity models through advanced analytics, adaptive assessments, and data-driven benchmarking.

The objective of this paper is to explore existing maturity models within the IS domain to determine whether common structure can be identified. For this purpose, a systematic literature review (SLR) was conducted to retrieve the largest possible range of relevant articles. Additionally, the study examines how emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence, influence the progression of maturity paths. To address this objective, the paper investigates the following research questions:

RQ1: Can common structural components, such as dimensions, maturity levels, and model typologies, be identified across maturity models in the IS domain?

RQ2: Do emerging technologies reshape the established maturity paths of IS maturity models?

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides a review of related work in the field, while Section 3 details the research methodology. Section 4 presents the research results, followed by Section 5, which provides an in-depth discussion with recommendations for future research, and Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. RELATED WORK

Information systems are critical for organizational performance, supporting strategic objectives and operational processes. Systematic literature reviews have been used to examine IS maturity models, providing insights into their structure and application. Selected review articles are presented in Table 1. The selection of these articles was based on their analysis of maturity models. Each article includes extensive coverage of digital libraries and presents detailed findings with clear and transparent reporting.

Table 1: Excerpts from literature reviews on maturity models

Paper	Scope	Sources	Time frame
(Becker et al., 2010)	research on maturity models; retrospection on previous and potential future research (20 articles)	ACM DL, AIS eLibrary, Emerald, ScienceDirect IEEE Xplore, ProQuest, Springer Link, Wiley	1994 – 2009
(Lasrado et al., 2015)	generic structure for MM, vocabulary and theoretical considerations in IS research (34 articles)	ACM Digital Library, AIS eLibrary, IEEE explore, Springer Link	1999 – 2014
(Mettler & Ballester, 2021)	methodological weaknesses of MM research, suggestions to improve design principles (129 articles)	Web of Science, AIS eLibrary	No limitations
(Poepelbuss et al., 2011)	research perspectives of MM; theoretical, publication, and practitioners (76 articles)	ACM DL, AIS eLibrary, ProQuest, EBSCOhost, Wiley, ScienceDirect	1996 – 2010

Examining the published literature reviews highlights the significance of maturity models while simultaneously revealing opportunities for additional insights by further reviewing the published research. Furthermore, particular attention is given to AI as a relatively novel and transformative technology with the potential to reshape maturity research. To ensure coverage of all relevant studies, the review includes an extensive set of digital libraries and is supplemented by backward citation searches.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopts the systematic literature review methodology proposed by Kitchenham (2007). The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines were used to improve the review process reporting. The search process began with the identification of relevant keywords and formulation of search strings. The term “information systems maturity model” was considered essential for retrieving relevant studies. The titles of publications were searched, as applying these terms to abstracts or full-text searches led to many irrelevant results. An example of a search string is as follows:

TITLE ((information system OR "IS") AND (maturit* OR capabilit* OR capacit* OR competenc* OR readiness) AND (model OR framework OR level OR assessment OR evaluation OR analysis OR measure*))

The search strategy included ACM Digital Library, IEEE Xplore, Scopus, ScienceDirect, and Web of Science as main databases, while Springer Link and AIS eLibrary served as supplementary sources. Certain databases, such as Google Scholar, were excluded due to their inclusion of non-peer-reviewed material. The search was conducted between September 2, 2025, and September 22, 2025. In total, 254 articles were initially retrieved

and imported into the Mendeley reference management system. In Stage 1 of screening process, article relevance to the review's focus was assessed based on the title. After the first exclusion, 58 articles remained for further consideration. In Stage 2, abstracts were analyzed, which led to the selection of 29 articles for full-text review. To capture additional relevant studies not identified in the initial search, backward snowballing was applied. Following the full-text review, a final set of 16 articles was included in the study. A set of inclusion (IC) and exclusion criteria (EC) was defined and applied in the screening process. Articles were included if they (IC1) proposed a model or framework for assessing maturity within the IS domain and (IC2) were published in academic outlets, specifically peer-reviewed journals or conference proceedings. Conversely, studies were excluded if they (EC1) focused on readiness assessment or only applied an existing model for maturity evaluation, (EC2) were not peer-reviewed or represented earlier versions of subsequently published papers, or (EC3) were not written in English. No restrictions were applied regarding the year of publication.

4. RESULTS

The final set of papers included in the review proposed models tailored to specific domains, such as healthcare, education, and the public sector, as well as for specific purposes including strategic planning and interoperability. This diversity provided a basis for examining whether a common structure of IS maturity models could be identified, thereby addressing RQ1. The complete list of reviewed papers is provided in Appendix 1. To ensure consistency and adherence to the same evaluation criteria, a predefined schema was used for data extraction from all papers included in the SLR. The analysis reveals some common characteristics in the design of IS maturity models (Table 2). Three papers addressed readiness assessment, which is conducted prior to the start of maturity process, while maturity evaluation positions the organization along a progressive maturity path (Ariansyah et al., 2025).

Table 2: Summary of SLR findings

Category	Value	Explanation
Research method	analytical	SLR findings used as the basis for model development, some studies complemented this approach with expert insights, typically gathered through interviews with domain specialists, to validate or refine the model
Design approach	bottom-up	assessment items are first identified during the design phase and subsequently maturity levels
Purpose of use	descriptive	model explains the current state of an organization's processes or capabilities, generally does not provide guidance on how to transition to higher levels of maturity
Design typology	structured model	hierarchical structure with formalized stages, where maturity levels reflect a progressive path
Assessment method	quantitative	models produce maturity scores that determine the organization's placement within a defined maturity level
Levels		number ranges from 3 to 9, five levels most common

The analysis also revealed a set of common dimensions across the maturity models, reflected in recurring assessment items (Table 3). These dimensions indicate similar foundations despite variations in model design or application.

Table 3: Common dimensions identified in MMs

Category proposed by model	Dimensions included in model
technological	infrastructure, system quality, information quality
organizational	organizational structure, size, culture, strategy and strategic alignment
human resources	people, communication, skills

5. DISCUSSION

This review identified a relatively small set of maturity models, with 16 papers included in the final analysis. Although number of models may constrain the generalizability of the findings, the diversity of application domains confirms the broad relevance of IS maturity models. Despite variations, the analysis revealed structural similarities across the models. Common dimensions, along with hierarchical design featuring formalized stages, suggest that IS maturity models often rely on shared foundations. At the same time, it is important to consider the influence of emerging technologies, particularly AI, on IS maturity models. Traditional maturity models typically emphasize linear progression, whereas AI has the potential to accelerate advancement through maturity stages. Low levels of AI adoption are generally associated with early maturity stages, yet frameworks that explicitly integrate AI into existing maturity models are still underdeveloped.

According to Nozari et al. (2024), the dimensions of IS maturity models most influenced by AI include infrastructure, data, and people. AI often requires advanced computing resources, thereby accelerating the need for robust technical foundations and changing expectations for technological capability. Equally critical is the reliance on high-quality data, which increases the importance of data availability, quality, governance, and integration within maturity assessments. From a human resources perspective, organizations must invest in employee training and skill development to enable effective AI integration into existing processes. This also includes evaluating how employees and AI systems complement one another in decision-making and task execution. In addition, AI raises governance-related considerations, including responsible use, data privacy, and regulatory compliance, all of which can reshape how governance is measured in maturity models. Beyond established dimensions, AI may necessitate the introduction of new ones, such as AI adoption, to assess the extent to which the technology is integrated across the organization, and AI governance, to capture both the evolving capabilities and risks associated with AI. On other hand, influence of AI on maturity is not uniform across dimensions. In some cases, it may accelerate maturity progression, for example, by rapidly advancing technological capabilities or improving process efficiency through automation. However, this growth can create imbalances. Other dimensions, such as

ethical governance, employee readiness, organizational culture, change management, may struggle to keep pace.

As part of future work, this research will be extended to include maturity models beyond the IS domain. The larger set of MMs will enable the generalizability of the findings. In addition, the impact of AI can be empirically validated by comparing organizations with high versus organizations with low levels of AI adoption, to see how maturity trajectories differ.

6. CONCLUSION

Information systems support operational efficiency and overall business performance. As organizations seek to adapt to an increasingly dynamic business environment, maturity models provide a structured approach to assessing current capabilities and identifying opportunities for improvement. Therefore, we conducted this SLR to gain knowledge from publications on this topic. In response to first research question, the findings indicate that maturity models in the IS domain share several characteristics, in terms of design approach, typology, and assessment methods. Across models, recurring dimensions include infrastructure, organizational structure, culture, strategy, people, and skills, suggesting the presence of shared foundations. In response to the second research question, AI has the potential to reshape established maturity paths, with infrastructure, data, and people being the most affected dimensions. Although studies included in this SLR do not explicitly confirm that AI accelerates progression through maturity stages, they indicate its growing influence on the factors underlying organizational maturity. Consequently, the actual impact of AI on maturity progression remains to be empirically validated. However, while AI may expedite advancement in certain areas, it may also negatively impact others, underscoring the need for careful analysis of its effects.

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